

STUDENTS' STUDY HABITS AND ITS IMPACTS ON THEIR ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the study habits of students and the relationship between these habits and their academic performance. The research focused on identifying preferred study habits, evaluating the perceived impact of these habits on academic performance, and analyzing the frequency and percentage of students' academic performances. Data revealed that among the study habits, including taking down notes, listening to music, group study, and recording, students preferred taking down notes the most. Students perceived these study habits as positively influencing their academic performance, evidenced by high mean scores in focus, comfort, and retention during study sessions. However, the study found no significant relationship between the preferred study habits and academic performance, nor between the perceived impact of these habits and academic outcomes. The findings suggest the importance of promoting effective study habits tailored to individual learning styles to enhance learning outcomes.

Keywords: *study habits, academic performance, academic outcomes, perceived impacts, Senior High School (SHS) students*

INTRODUCTION

The global academic calendar was in disarray due to the coronavirus outbreak. Due to the pandemic, most classes were on hold, and some schools were shut down. To resume classes, online distance learning was acknowledged as a solution to the problem, which was favorable during that time and is still used today (UNESCO, 2020). As stated by Niemi and Kousa (2020), the experiences of students aged between 16 and 18 during the COVID-19 pandemic revealed that the students had problems such as motivation, concentration, and learning difficulties, which caused changes in their study habits due to "home-based" distance learning. Furthermore, study habits and attitudes were crucial for students to be efficient in their learning. Recognizing and applying these habits could significantly enhance a student's learning methods, as they were a significant determinant of their academic performance (Tus, 2020).

Salcedo-Relucio (2019) found that there was a positive relationship between study habits and academic performance; thus, having consistent study habits could lead to better academic performance. However, different extracurricular activities could cause students' learning and study habits to decline due to a lack of focus on their studies, which could affect their understanding of topics (Capuno et al., 2019). Moreover, learning styles or study habits referred to how students learned and processed information. These study habits helped ensure a more effective learning experience for all students (Magulod Jr., 2019).

The research study conducted by Goud (2018) revealed that there is a positive relationship towards study habits and academic achievements of the students. His study is focused on the gender, locality, and school management type and how does this influence students' academic achievement and how does these factors influence students' study habits. In this study, the researchers give emphasis on the importance of taking down notes and listening to music as one of the way students' study, how these study habits impacts their academic performance, and how does the perceived impact of study habits also affects their academic performance.

The majority of the students' problems, as observed by the researchers, were that students only reviewed when an exam was approaching; in other words, they crammed. The purpose of this study was to determine their study habits and to assess the impact of various study habits on their academic performance. It also aimed to contribute data and information that could help enhance the study habits and academic performance of the students.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to examine the study habits of the students and to investigate the relationship between study habits and the academic performance of the students. This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. Which of the following study habits are preferred by the students:

- 1.1 Taking down notes;
- 1.2 Listening music;
- 1.3 Group study; and
- 1.4 Recording?
2. What is the perceived impact of students' study habits on their academic performance in terms of the following aspects:
 - 2.1 Focus;
 - 2.2 Comfort; and
 - 2.3 Retention?
3. What is the academic performance of the students?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the students' preferred study habits and its impact on their academic performance?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the students' perceived impact of their study habits and their academic performance?

METHODOLOGY

Data and Respondents

The respondents consisted of senior high school students at Metro Dumaguete College during the school year 2023-2024. With a total population of 156 students in the Senior High School Department, a sample size of 112 was selected using systematic random sampling for data collection. The following data reflect the distribution of the respondents.

Year/Level	Population (N)	Sample (n)
Grade 12	86	62
Grade 11	70	50
Total	156	112

This study employed a descriptive-correlational design. It was descriptive because it (a) described various study habits and (b) examined the effects of these different study habits on students' academic performance. It also utilized correlation analysis to explore the relationship between students' study habits and their academic performance. This study was conducted at Metro Dumaguete College, Incorporated located at E.J. Blanco Drive Extension, Daro, Dumaguete City, Negros Oriental. It is a private school founded and owned by Mr. Wilfredo S. Manila and his beloved wife Dr. Delma P. Manila on August 13, 2002. The school envisions being the school of choice in 2030. True to its vision, it is now one of the fast-growing schools in Dumaguete City with over 1,000 students and more than 100 faculty members. Metro Dumaguete College Incorporated Offers Senior

High School, Baccalaureate Programs, Three-Year Diploma Courses, and Technical Vocational Education. For Senior High School, they offer the following tracks: Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM), Humanities and Social Science (HUMSS), General Academic Strand (GAS), Technical Vocational Livelihood - Information and Communications Technology (TVL - ICT), and Technical Vocational Livelihood - Home Economics (TVL - HE). It also offers a unique curriculum for its three-year diploma programs: Diploma in Tourism Technology (DToT), Diploma in Digital Arts Technology (DDAT), Diploma in Software Engineering Technology (DSET), and Diploma in Vocational Teacher Education Technology (DVTET). Additionally, for its baccalaureate programs, they offer Bachelor of Science in Computer Science major in Software Engineering, Bachelor of Science in Information Technology major in Digital Arts, Bachelor of Science in Business Administration major in Financial Management, Bachelor of Science in Business Administration major in Marketing Management, Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management, Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education major in Computer Hardware Servicing, Animation, and Computer Programming. Metro Dumaguete College, Incorporated is also a Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) recognized assessment center for Animation NCII, Java Programming NCIV, Bookkeeping NCIL, Contact Center Services NCII, and Computer Systems Servicing NCII (Metro Dumaguete College, 2023). Furthermore, Metro Dumaguete College Incorporated offers the following facilities: Business and Finance Office, MDC Library, Office of the Registrar and Admission, Office of the Student Affairs and Services, Health Services Office, Guidance Office, Nuestra Señora de Fatima Chapel, Gymnasium, Open Ground, Computer Laboratory, Speech Laboratory, Robotics Laboratory, Animation Laboratory, Housekeeping Laboratory, and Cookery Laboratory.

Ethical considerations were rigorously integrated throughout this research study on the study habits of Senior High students and their effects on academic performance. Given the involvement of human participants, confidentiality of information was upheld, and dignity was maintained. Finally, respondents in the study were requested to provide informed consent, signifying their full understanding of the study's risks and benefits, thus reinforcing the ethical conduct of this research endeavor.

The researchers integrated all the corrections and suggestions of panelists. Afterwards, a letter of request to conduct this study was sent to the President of Metro Dumaguete College, Dr. Delma P. Manila, upon the approval of the Vice President of Academic Affairs, Dr. Eva C. Melon, and Senior High School Department, Principal, Mr. Renze O. Lagrada. Afterwards, the signed and approved letter of request to conduct a study is presented to the SHS Principal. Moreover, during the distribution, the researchers explained to the respondents the purpose and importance of the study and assured them that any data collected will remain confidential. Furthermore, the research instruments were retrieved after the students have provided all the required information. In addition, the results are tallied and shown using Microsoft Excel, which is then analyzed and interpreted by the researchers' statistician.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

The researchers will utilize the following tools in analyzing and interpreting the study's data:

Mean. This was used to evaluate (a) the students study habits and (b) the perceived impacts of study habits to the student's academic performance.

Spearman rank correlation coefficient. This was utilized to identify the degree of relationship between the students study habits and the perceived impacts of the students study habits on the student's academic performance.

The following interpretations were applied by the researchers to describe the extent of students' study habits:

Score	Verbal Description	Explanation
5	Strongly Agree	The use of students' study habit is very high.
4	Agree	The use of students' study habit is high.
3	Neutral	The use of students' study habit is moderate.
2	Disagree	The use of students' study habit is low.
1	Strongly Disagree	The use of students' study habit is very low.

The following interpretation was used to describe the relationship between the variables:

Score	Verbal Description	Explanation
5	Strongly Agree	The study habits and its impact have a 81-100% relationship.
4	Agree	The study habits and its impact have a 61-80% relationship.
3	Neutral	The study habits and its impact have a 41-60% relationship.
2	Disagree	The study habits and its impact have a 21-40% relationship.
1	Strongly Disagree	The study habits and its impact have a 1-20% relationship.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1.1 presents the data on the extent of taking down notes preferred by the students. Based on the results, taking down notes helps them remember the topic, enhance their understanding of complex lessons, enhances their comprehension skills. Taking down notes have an “high” verbal equivalent with an overall weighted mean of ($w\bar{x} = 3.88$), which implies that the respondents believe that taking down notes helps improve their study habit. This aligns on Gorospe and Abad (2023) finding where note-taking improves the overall grade of the students and Salame and Thompson (2020) also found that strategic note-taking can help student perform well in class. Furthermore, learning strategies like taking notes are crucial for students' progress and academic achievement. These strategies help students remember important information and avoid unfamiliarity, ensuring they do not repeat unfamiliar concepts (Agustin et al., 2021).

Table 1.1
Extent of Taking Down Notes preferred by the Students

Taking down notes	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Equivalent
1) Helps me remember and understands the topic better.	3.98	High
2) It helps enhance my understanding of complex lessons.	3.91	High
3) It helps me enhance my capability in remembering a topic.	3.83	High
4) It enhances my comprehension in reading or listening lessons.	3.88	High
5) It improves my retention.	3.79	High
Composite	3.88	High

Legend: Scale Verbal Equivalent

4.21 – 5.00	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Very Low

Table 1.2 highlights the result of the extent of listening to music preferred by the students which has a “high” verbal equivalent with an average of ($w\bar{x} = 3.63$). Listening to music helps them remember the topic, enhances their understanding of complex lessons and comprehension skills. This further implies that listening to music also helps enhance their study habit. This result aligns with the study of de la Mora Velasco and Hirumi (2020) which reviews how background music affects learning, highlighting the benefits of instrumental and ambient music in improving focus and retention, while also noting potential distractions from music with lyrics. The various benefits of listening to music includes its ability to improve mood and cognitive functions, thereby enhancing study effectiveness when the right type of music is chosen (Cherry, 2019). Maynes-Blanco and Nartea (2020) also found that music is widely listened to by students but its

impact on academic performance varies, with no significant relationship found between music and overall grades, but listening to music is a factor influencing the students' academic experiences.

Table 1.2
Extent of Listening to Music preferred by the Students

Listening to Music	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Equivalent
1) Helps me remember and understands the topic better.	3.72	High
2) It helps enhance my understanding of complex lessons.	3.6	High
3) It helps me enhance my capability in remembering a topic.	3.57	High
4) It enhances my comprehension in reading or listening lessons.	3.67	High
5) It improves my retention.	3.6	High
Composite	3.63	High

Legend: Scale Verbal Equivalent

4.21 – 5.00	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Very Low

Table 1.3 shows the extent of group study preferred by the students which results with a verbal equivalent “high” with an average of ($w\bar{x} = 3.64$). Group study helps them remember the topic, enhance their understanding of complex lessons, and improves their retention. This indicates that group study helps improves the study habits of the students.

According to Cheng et al. (2021), the level of collaborative learning is important to the engagement of students in the classroom as it can help them enhance their creativity and empathy and also enable them to contribute their knowledge and learn from each other in the process. Cooperative learning influences university students' academic goals, including learning, social reinforcement, and achievement goals and it is effective in motivating students to engage deeply with their tasks and develop essential skills (Mendo-Lázaro et al., 2022) and that group discussions and cooperative learning environments significantly enhance critical thinking abilities (Johar et al., 2023).

Table 1.3
Extent of Group Study preferred by the Students

Group Study	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Equivalent
1) Helps me remember and understands the topic better.	3.75	High
2) It helps enhance my understanding of complex lessons.	3.59	High
3) It helps me enhance my capability in remembering a topic.	3.64	High
4) It enhances my comprehension in reading or listening lessons.	3.6	High

5) It improves my retention.	3.63	High
Composite	3.64	High

Legend: Scale Verbal Equivalent

- 4.21 – 5.00 Very High
- 3.41 – 4.20 High
- 2.61 – 3.40 Moderate
- 1.81 – 2.60 Low
- 1.00 – 1.80 Very Low

Table 1.4 presents the data on the extent of recording preferred by the students and the results indicates that recording has a verbal equivalent “high” with an average of ($w\bar{x} = 3.46$). Based upon the result, recording helps them remember the topic, enhances their understanding of complex lessons and comprehension skills. This further implies that recording helps improve their study habit.

Ali (2019) and Zhang et al. (2022) results conclude that the usage and watching of video recordings or educational videos has a strong positive impact on student’s activities and performance. Moreover, online teaching methods such as recorded video and live broadcasting help improve academic performance, but the study found that live broadcasting teaching is more effective because it encourages more teacher-student interaction (Yao et al., 2020).

Table 1.4
Extent of Recording preferred by the Students

Recording	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Equivalent
1) Helps me remember and understands the topic better.	3.55	High
2) It helps enhance my understanding of complex lessons.	3.46	High
3) It helps me enhance my capability in remembering a topic.	3.34	High
4) It enhances my comprehension in reading or listening lessons.	3.54	High
5) It improves my retention.	3.42	High
Composite	3.46	High

Legend: Scale Verbal Equivalent

- 4.21 – 5.00 Very High
- 3.41 – 4.20 High
- 2.61 – 3.40 Moderate
- 1.81 – 2.60 Low
- 1.00 – 1.80 Very Low

Table 2.1 presents the data on the perceived impact of students’ study habits on their academic performance in terms of focus and the results show that focus has an average of ($w\bar{x} = 3.68$) with a verbal description “high”. Based on the results, they understand the lesson, memorize, and comprehend easily due to focus. This implies that the respondents

believe that focus has a positive impact on their academic performance. Students often find it difficult to focus and concentrate on studying when they get distracted by their surroundings, which has an impact on their learning (Rotas & Cahapay, 2020). The study of Bos et al. (2019) examines that an educational technology innovation such as Augmented Reality (AR) can enhance students focus and concentration when used appropriately, and concentration mostly influence students' learning quality (Le, 2021).

Table 2.1
Perceived Impact of Students' Study Habits on their Academic Performance in terms of Focus.

Focus	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Equivalent
1) It is easy for me to memorize information.	3.79	High
2) It is easy for me to enhance my comprehension.	3.68	High
3) It is easy for me to grasp and retain lessons.	3.58	High
4) It is easy for me to understand the lessons.	3.85	High
5) It is easy for me to learn and adapt new study technique.	3.51	High
Composite	3.68	High
Legend: Scale	Verbal Equivalent	
4.21 – 5.00	Very High	
3.41 – 4.20	High	
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate	
1.81 – 2.60	Low	
1.00 – 1.80	Very Low	

Table 2.2 shows the results of the perceive impact of students' study habits on their academic performance in terms of comfort which has a verbal equivalent "high" and an average of ($w\bar{x} = 3.78$). The results indicate that they can memorize information, grasp and retain lessons, and can enhance comprehension easily due to comfort. This means that comfort has an impact on student's academic performance. Children's academic abilities are influenced by classroom indoor climate parameters such as ventilation and lighting. It is said that good lighting and a proper ventilation rate improve students' concentration as well as their academic performance (Hviid et al., 2020). The school's physical environment affects the academic performance of the students as students who engage with a pleasant physical environment perform better than students whose learning environment is not conducive (Baafi, 2020). Similarly, uncomfortable and unsafe online classroom conditions, such as exposure to extreme temperatures, loud noises or even quiet spaces, and lighting, can negatively impact students' academic performance (Zhong et al., 2019).

Table 2.2***Perceived Impact of Students' Study Habits on their Academic Performance in terms of Comfort.***

Comfort	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Equivalent
1) It is easy for me to memorize information.	3.96	High
2) It is easy for me to enhance my comprehension.	3.73	High
3) It is easy for me to grasp and retain lessons.	3.78	High
4) It is easy for me to understand the lessons.	3.72	High
5) It is easy for me to learn and adapt new study technique.	3.71	High
Composite	3.78	High

Legend: Scale Verbal Equivalent

4.21 – 5.00	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Very Low

Table 2.3 highlights the results of the perceived impact of students' study habits on their academic performance in terms of retention which indicates that retention helps students grasp and retain lessons, memorize information, and enhance comprehension easily. The results indicates that the impact of retention on their academic performance has a verbal equivalent "high" and an average of ($w\bar{x} = 3.60$). This implies that retention has an impact on the academic performance of the students.

The findings are in line with Glew et al. (2019), which indicate that there is a relationship between students's academic support, retention, and academic performance. Michael et al. (2020) also found that students who have study skills training perform better academically and are able to retain knowledge better. Furthermore, innovative teaching strategies, such as fostering a positive attitude, collaborative learning, and developing language convergence and information sources, can help students learn, retain, and perform better academically (Buga-ay & Causing, 2023).

Table 2.3***Perceived Impact of Students' Study Habits on their Academic Performance in terms of Retention.***

Retention	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Equivalent
1) It is easy for me to memorize information.	3.63	High
2) It is easy for me to enhance my comprehension.	3.58	High
3) It is easy for me to grasp and retain lessons.	3.65	High
4) It is easy for me to understand the lessons.	3.58	High
5) It is easy for me to learn and adapt new study technique.	3.57	High
Composite	3.60	High

Legend: Scale	Verbal Equivalent
4.21 – 5.00	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Very Low

Table 3 presents the academic performance of the students, with the total sample size of 112 students. Based on the data, 39.3% has an outstanding performance followed by 36.6% got the very satisfactory and 6.2% got fairly satisfactory performance. This implies that majority of the students perform well academically. Similar to these finding, Islam (2021) found that students with proper study habits are more likely to achieve positive academic results, while those with poor habits (i.e., an inappropriate study schedule and poor learning techniques) are more likely to lead to academic failure. In addition, factors including interest, parental understanding, teacher-student interaction (Davarinia et al., 2020), motivation, student competency, and satisfaction (Lin et al., 2023) can influence students' academic success and enhances their academic performance.

Table 3
Academic Performance of the Students.

Grade Descriptors	Range	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	90-100	44	39.3%
Very Satisfactory	85-89	41	36.6%
Satisfactory	80-84	20	17.9%
Fairly Satisfactory	75-79	7	6.2%
Did Not Meet Expectations	Below 75	0	0
Total		112	100%

Legend: Scale	Verbal Equivalent
4.21 – 5.00	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Very Low

Table 4 shows the relationship between the students' study habits and impact on their academic performance and it indicates that there is no significant relationship between the preferred study habits, which are taking down notes, listening to music, group study, and recording, and their academic performance. This findings aligns with Castillo et al. (2023) where there is indeed a significant relation between how a person studies and how it affects the outcome of their performance and study habits is one of the factor that may influence the academic performance of a student. Dalmolin et al. (2018) and Magulod Jr. (2019) also found that there is a positive relationship between learning styles and students' academic performance.

Table 4***Relationship between the Students' Preferred Study Habits and Impact on their Academic Performance***

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Academic Performance				
Taking Down Notes	0.828	0.084	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant
Listening Music	0.337	0.580	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant
Group Study	0.436	0.463	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant
Recording	0.284	0.644	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant

Table 5 shows the relationship between the students' perceived impact and their academic performance and the results indicate that the students' perceived impact; focus, comfort, and retention has no significant relationship on their academic performance. This aligns to a study by Liu et al. (2021) where comfort within school environment is important in students' academic performance, as it significantly impacts their learning ability. Also, teachers' ability to deliver lessons effectively has the highest influence on students' retention (Bombaes, 2021) and can increase students' focus in learning (Erwiza et al., 2019).

Table 5***Relationship between the Students' Perceived Impact and their Academic Performance***

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Academic Performance				
Focus	0.338	0.578	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
Comfort	0.659	0.226	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
Retention	0.360	0.551	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant

Recommendations

In light of the finding and conclusions presented, the following are recommended to teachers and students:

Students:

They actively engaged in note-taking, chose music that helped concentration, participated in group study sessions, and utilized recordings for supplementary review. Adapting these study habits to their individual learning styles maximized their learning outcomes and achieved academic success.

Teachers:

Firstly, they provided guidance on effective study techniques tailored to individual learning styles, such as note-taking methods and listening to music skills.

Secondly, they integrated technology effectively into teaching practices and fostered a positive and inclusive learning environment that enhanced students' engagement and motivation.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

For the length of the study, the researchers were demonstrating all relevant ethical principles. The confidentiality of the information was preserved because humans was be the study's subjects.

All the necessary ethical considerations were observed by the researchers during the entire duration of the study. Confidentiality was observed to ensure privacy of the information extracted from the respondents. The researchers also adhered to the ethical protocols stipulated in the Ethics Committee of Metro Dumaguete College Inc. In addition, the researchers sought permission from the proper authorities before conducting the study.

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